

Aviation Zero Emissions 2050 (AZERO)

D1.1

Data Management Plan

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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN¹

Project Details

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HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	17.02.2025	Initial version of DMP
1.1	21.02.2025	DMP version submitted to the EU Portal during Month 6 (M6) of the project

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¹ This DMP uses the template of the EU Grants: Data management plan (HE): V1.1 – 01.04.2022

Contents

1. Project Summary	4
2. Data Summary	4
3. FAIR data	4
3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	4
3.2. Making data accessible	5
3.3. Making data interoperable	5
3.4. Increase data re-use	5
4. Other research outputs	6
5. Data security	6
6. Ethics	7
7. Other issues	7

1. Project Summary

Decarbonisation of Aviation will require strict regulation and monitoring to be aligned with the EU Green Deal in making the EU the world's first climate neutral region by 2050. EU regulation is continuously evolving, affecting key performance indicators (KPIs) used to measure this ambitious objective. The overall goal of this project is to contribute to the decarbonisation of aviation by assessing airline reduction commitments for achieving net zero carbon by 2050.

Applying an interdisciplinary approach, the methodology is divided into three stages: 1) Mapping all the GHG KPIs used by European airlines, to set up targets and follow-up measures; 2) Evaluating the actions taken and planned to reach net zero carbon by European airlines, applying a supervised automatic textual analysis to airline ESG reports - a new source of data not used in the past in the airline industry; and 3) Simulate via traffic scenarios, environmental initiatives and airline commitments to estimate the KPIs feasibility using the System Dynamic (SD) method for the timeframes of 2030, 2040 and 2050.

2. Data Summary

The AZERO project will generate both qualitative and quantitative data. Qualitative data will be derived from the literature review of existing regulations and textual analysis of airline sustainability reports, while quantitative data will include GHG KPIs extracted from these reports. Additionally, simulation data from SD models will provide insights into the feasibility of emission reduction initiatives for the timeframes of 2030, 2040, and 2050. The data formats will include .csv, .xlsx, and .pdf files, with an estimated total volume of approximately 10 GB. The data will be generated from publicly available sustainability reports and simulations conducted within the project. This data is intended to support researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders in assessing the aviation sector's progress toward decarbonisation. All the collected and generated data will be made available on the Zenodo data repository, for which further details are provided in the next section.

The project will also generate research output in the form of academic manuscripts. The hosting institution, DCU, is a member of the Irish HEIs consortium that has agreements with academic publishers to make their research open and accessible. Thus, three research papers will be published in open access at quality peer-reviewed academic journals. AZERO will also publish the conference paper on EU Airline ESG Reporting on the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform because the fellow is a strong supporter of open research, having personally financed the gold access fee for some of his past publications. This recent European open research initiative seems very promising and he wants both to use and support it. All these publications will be made available through the Open AIRE platform that is described in more detailed below.

3. FAIR data

The AZERO project is using FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) principles.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The AZERO project uses the OpenAIRE platform, which is the major EC-supported initiative for fostering open science in Europe. OpenAIRE is a non-profit organization with a mission to promote open scholarship and improve discoverability, accessibility, shareability, reusability, reproducibility, and monitoring of data-driven research results, globally. This platform will act as the main project hub, together with the project website azero2050.eu, interconnecting all the data

used and generated in the project. One account has already been created for the AZERO project, showing the summary created by CORDIS and being linked to data used for the research².

The ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) will be used by fellow and supervisors in the project. This unique research identifier enhances the discoverability of research outputs by providing a persistent identifier that links their work across platforms, publishers, and institutions. This ensures that publications, datasets, and other contributions are accurately attributed, even in cases of name variations or changes.

Lastly, to ensure consistency and discoverability, structured naming conventions (e.g., ZERO_GHG_KPIs_2030.csv) will be applied. Metadata will also be optimized for search engines by including relevant keywords.

3.2. Making data accessible

The research data and the publications from the AZERO project have already started to be deposited on the Zenodo platform, which is an EU-supported portal for big data management and offers extended digital library capabilities for open access and open data. For example, the set of data with airlines annual and sustainability reports for 2023 used for the project can now be found on Zenodo³, which allows the research community to use it freely by providing the corresponding references⁴.

Data collected and generated for the research will be placed in the Zenodo repository and properly linked to the OpenAIRE platform. Thus, all the project data, both used and created, will be easily discoverable and will be open access.

3.3. Making data interoperable

To maximize interoperability, data formats such as .csv, .xlsx and PDF will be used to ensure compatibility across platforms. Anyone with basic computer skills will be able to open and use the data.

Zenodo follows DataCite Metadata Schema (<https://schema.datacite.org/>) which is a list of core metadata properties chosen for an accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes, along with recommended use instructions. Hence, the AZERO metadata will be fully interoperable.

Part of the aim of the project is to map all the different environmental KPIs related to emissions used by European airlines. In this context, the different ontologies used will be made available in the first academic publication planned.

3.4. Increase data re-use

All the project output, including the data, will be released with the Creative Commons license (CC BY). This license allows re-users to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, as long as attribution is given to the creator. The license allows for commercial use.

Documentation accompanying each dataset will include detailed descriptions of methodologies,

² AZERO project at Open AIRE Platform

https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_____he::69f244052eb19347d26c6d1a38467770

³ AZERO project data set at Zenodo Platform <https://zenodo.org/records/14876202>

⁴ MARTÍN-DOMINGO, L. (2023–2024). European Public Listed Airlines Annual and Sustainability Reports 2023 [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14876202>

variable definitions, units of measurement, and any pre-processing steps taken. Data quality assurance processes will ensure accuracy and reliability.

The project aims to publish three open access articles under the Creative Commons license in order to allow for a possibly widest possible re-use of the research output. As outlined in section 3.2, the research data from the AZERO project will be deposited on Zenodo for open access. The research data and metadata will be freely available on Zenodo without any restrictions.

Any other research output (such as posters and presentations) will be made available online on the project's website and social media and widely shared. Their re-use will be encouraged, and there will be no restrictions on copying or distributing the materials.

4. Other research outputs

Making the research open and available to the research community will be complemented by making the same research accessible to a wider range of stakeholders, especially policy makers, airlines and the general public. The research paper's content will be simplified, summarized and made available in different formats (i.e. text, short video presentations and podcast).

The simplified content of research papers will be sent for publication at The Conversation⁵, which is an independent, non-profit news platform that publishes research-based articles written by academics and edited by journalists, aiming to make expert knowledge accessible to the public. In addition, all those additional research output formats will be made available at the project website.

Providing research outputs in diverse formats, such as text, videos, and podcasts, supports the FAIR principles by enhancing Findability through wider dissemination across platforms and improving Accessibility with user-friendly formats for varied audiences. Hosting these outputs on the project website ensures open access, while their structured presentation promotes Reusability for educational and professional purposes, extending the research's impact beyond academia.

Allocation of resources

The costs associated with making data FAIR—including storage, archiving, and open-access publishing—are covered under the Horizon Europe grant budget. Dublin City University (DCU) is responsible for managing these resources. Long-term preservation costs are minimized through the use of institutional repositories like OpenAIRE.

5. Data security

Data security measures include storage on two secure drives: the laptop of the fellow and the host institution DCU's OneDrive webspace with regular backups to prevent loss. Access to the project data is restricted to authorized personnel within the project team. Secure transfer protocols will be put in place for sharing data with collaborators during the secondment at the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS). Recovery systems ensure that all data can be restored in case of accidental deletion or hardware failure. The content of the project website is managed only by the fellow and the hosting provider makes daily backups of their servers.

The data will be stored in at least two separate locations to avoid data loss. The data will not be transferred on USB drives. Any data will only be stored on password-protected devices. Data on the hosting institution server will have two-steps authentication. All data will be labelled in a systematic

⁵⁵ <https://theconversation.com/europe>

way in order to ensure coherence and transparency. In addition, depositing data on Zenodo is free of charge and allows for long-term preservation and curation in compliance with EU guidelines.

6. Ethics

AZERO will not collect personal data from members of the public for use within the project. The proposed research complies with legal and ethical requirements for Ireland (the host country) and the European Union. It aims to comply with the highest standards in research ethics and integrity, and the fellow is also committed to following the advice and guidelines provided by the host institution on research ethics and integrity.

This research will use “supervised automatic textual analysis methods,” which fall under the category of Artificial Intelligence (AI). In particular, the AI tool used will allow extracting and categorising text from the environmental section of airline’s ESG reports in relations to decarbonisation actions by European airlines.

In relation to AI, the project will not develop a new AI tool but will instead use an open source AI tool whenever possible for this purpose. The tool will be selected at the due time as this type of technology evolves at a fast pace. The AI tool will be mainly used for data extraction, a process which will be supervised with the ultimate aim of automating it for the future use after the project’s conclusion. The project will follow the guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research⁶, as defined by EU Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, which adhere to four principles: Reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability.

7. Other issues

The project includes a secondment at Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS) and data related issues, if any, will be updated when doing the secondment.

⁶ EU. (2024). Living guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2b6cf7e5-36ac-41cb-aab5-0d32050143dc_en?filename=ec_rtd_ai-guidelines.pdf